

Submerged Strategies

Rulebook

Preface

*S*ubmerged Strategies is a board wargame, specifically a skirmish game where two players compete within a modern underwater environment. The opposition is asymmetrical : each player takes control of an underwater drone with unique characteristics, actions, and objectives.

The game is played "double-blind" so that players do not see the opponent's pawn, similar to the principle of Battleship : the terrain map is duplicated, and a screen placed between the players' spaces prevents visibility of the opponent's terrain.

Furthermore, in this first version, the game also requires the intervention of a third person who takes the role of a gamemaster and also possesses a game map. The gamemaster or referee controls the flow of the game : they execute the actions decided by the players and manage interactions between them.

Although the primary goal of designing this game was to create a platform for developing AI planners to replace human players, the physical version is varied, original, and offers good balance as well as interesting gameplay.

Context

The game scenario is set in a military context : in a fully mapped underwater zone, an allied reconnaissance drone monitors the surroundings. It is then alerted to the appearance of a second suspicious drone at a certain known position on the terrain. The reconnaissance drone must determine the intentions of the suspicious drone before the latter completes its mission.

The suspect may be an ally, a neutral scientific drone, or constitute a threat to the reconnaissance drone's government. In the latter case, the reconnaissance drone will be forced to neutralize it.

Will the suspect drone complete its mission before the reconnaissance drone determines its intentions and blocks it ?

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A. Components

The game box includes the following components :

- * 3 game boards
- * 3 screens
- * 1 blue drone pawn on a base
- * 1 red drone pawn on a base
- * 2 blue drone pawns without a base
- * 2 red drone pawns without a base
- * 2 blue sliders (energy gauges)
- * 2 red sliders (energy gauges)
- * 16 action cards with blue backs
- * 21 action cards with red backs
- * 1 smart imagery failure card (red back)
- * 9 mission cards with white backs
- * 1 blue storage box for cards
- * 1 red storage box for cards
- * 3 blue card holders
- * 3 red card holders
- * 1 laminated sheet for reconnaissance drone actions
- * 9 laminated sheets for suspect drone missions and actions
- * 2 non-oriented tokens to represent the opposing drone
- * 6 brown domes representing decoys
- * 1 six-sided die
- * 1 eight-sided die
- * 1 triangular template with a side of 4 hexagons
- * 1 triangular template with a side of 12 hexagons
- * 1 circular template for a cluster of 7 hexagons
- * 1 large ruler

B. Goal of the Game and Victory Conditions

The game takes place in an underwater universe where each player embodies a drone.

One of the players takes control of an allied reconnaissance drone that we will call **Reco** and the second player directs **Suspect**, a drone with a secret mission randomly assigned using a deck from a set of nine mission cards.

The nine possible missions for Suspect are of neutral, allied, or enemy types, with three different missions for each type (*see section L.*).

The victory conditions for the players are :

- ▶ Reco wins the game if they manage to determine Suspect's mission and block them ; specifically, if Suspect is an enemy drone, then Reco must destroy it, and if Suspect is allied or neutral, then Reco must alert their hierarchy by informing them of Suspect's mission (*as detailed in section I., Reco can destroy Suspect using a torpedo shot and is also capable of warning their hierarchy using a communication node or by deploying a communication buoy to the surface.*).
- ▶ Suspect wins the game if they successfully complete their mission before Reco determines their intentions and blocks them or reveals their intentions to the government. Also, if Reco is mistaken about Suspect's mission by communicating the wrong mission to their hierarchy, or by destroying Suspect when the latter is not an enemy, then victory is

also awarded to the Suspect player.

The game is based on an energy management system, with each action costing the player a certain number of energy points ; charging stations present on the map allow players to recover energy instead. If a player runs out of energy before completing their mission, they lose the game.

- ▶ Reco or Suspect wins the game if their opponent runs out of energy during the encounter.

Finally, certain tiles on the terrain may contain mines (*see section F.*). If a drone leaves such a tile and it has not yet been cleared, it explodes and loses the game.

- ▶ Reco or Suspect wins the game if their opponent explodes while leaving a tile containing a mine.

C. Setup

The two competing players choose their role : one embodies Reco while the other controls the Suspect drone. The game requires the presence of a third person as a referee.

The material associated with the Reco player is blue, while that of the Suspect player is red.

The two players sit face to face at a table with a map in front of each of them and a screen to separate them. The other two screens are used to isolate a third map dedicated to the referee, set up next to the players' space.

On the game setup diagram above, the black bands designate the screens and the large rectangles the game boards. The blue dot represents Reco's starting area and the red dot that of Suspect.

Each player is then given the drone pawn on a base of the associated color and the slider representing the energy gauge, initially set to 40 points.

The game proceeds as follows :

- The Suspect player randomly draws a mission card, which determines their objective.
- The gamemaster gives each player a laminated sheet reminding them of their mission and possible actions each turn. Reco's sheet is visible, while Suspect's, which varies according to the mission drawn, must remain hidden. Action cards are also distributed to each player (*these are always the same for Reco, whereas they vary for Suspect depending on the mission*).
- The player controlling Reco starts on the blue tile marked with an "R" located at one end of the map.

- The player controlling Suspect starts on one of the red tiles marked with an "S" located at the other end of the map and numbered from 1 to 5. They choose one of them according to their strategy and must openly declare this location to all players.

- Both players secretly choose a starting orientation. The drone's orientation is necessarily perpendicular to a side of the hexagon (*thus, there are six possible orientations for a drone on a given tile*).

D. Game Progress

The game is played double-blind so that neither player sees the opponent's pawn. A gamemaster is required, as well as a system of action cards : each turn, players choose one and only one action and give a face-down card to the gamemaster, who then resolves both actions simultaneously on the boards.

Specifically, the game proceeds as follows :

- The game is played turn-by-turn as specified above ; each player performs exactly one action per turn, and actions are resolved simultaneously by the gamemaster.
- In addition to the action decided by the player, a passive sonar ping is performed at the start of each turn (*this systematic and energy-free action is explained in section H. of the manual*).
- The game then continues until one of the two players wins by reaching their objective or loses by falling to 0 on their energy gauge or exploding on a mine (*see section B.*).

E. Terrain Map

The terrain map is represented as a hexagonal grid (*often called a honeycomb grid*). Oriented as in the figure below, the map contains 17 rows numbered from 0 to 16, each consisting of 21 or 22 hexagons, with odd rows shifted to the right.

Hexagons are associated with underwater environmental elements such as currents, reefs, or rocks, for example. Other tiles represent special mechanisms useful in the game, such as energy charging stations or communication nodes. Finally, certain locations on the board are intended for Suspect's missions, which appear in red on the map.

Here is the game map :

The possible missions for the Suspect drone are divided into three zones, and each zone involves three missions : one neutral, one allied, and one enemy mission (*see section L.*).

At the top of the map (*rows 0 and 1*), a fiber optic cable is shown ; it constitutes the first mission zone. Toward the center of the map, two hydrothermal vents are shown within a partially mined region, corresponding to the second mission zone. Finally, at the bottom of the map (*row 15*), a pipeline with a damaged section is present ; this is associated with the third mission zone.

F. Terrain Elements

The functions of the terrain elements present on the map are explained here.

▼ Sedimentary Plain

This unconstrained tile affects neither drone movements nor their actions (*242 tiles of this type, or roughly 63% of the terrain*).

▼ Reef

This tile increases the energy cost of movement by 1 point when passing through it or stopping on it (*13 reef tiles on the terrain*).

▼ Rock

This tile increases the energy cost of movement by 2 points when passing through it or stopping on it (*19 rock tiles on the terrain*).

▼ Mountain

This tile is inaccessible; it must be bypassed (*6 mountain tiles on the terrain*). Furthermore, it prevents passive and active sonar, magnetometer, and ML camera detections if the mountain is located on the line connecting the two drones (*see sections H. and I.*).

▼ Algae

This tile is blocking : it cannot be crossed in a single move, and one must stop on it (*10 algae tiles on the terrain*).

▼ Current

This tile is semi-blocking : depending on the angle between the direction of movement and the direction of the current, passing through this tile results in an energy bonus (*tailcurrent*) or an energy penalty (*counter-current*).

Details regarding the rules and energy costs associated with currents are explained in the following section (*39 current tiles on the terrain*).

▼ Acoustic Interference Zone

This special tile represents a sonar undetectability zone : passive and active sonars cannot detect a drone located there (*one acoustic interference zone on the terrain consisting of 11 tiles*).

▼ Blind Zone

This special tile represents an ML smart imagery undetectability zone : Reco cannot detect Suspect or obtain information about its equipment if Suspect is on one of these tiles (*one blind zone on the terrain consisting of 4 tiles*).

▼ Communication Node

This tile is useful for Reco, who can communicate with their hierarchy to declare Suspect's mission if they are on the tile or within a distance of 1 hexagon from it (*5 communication node tiles on the terrain*).

▼ Charging Station

This tile allows drones in proximity to recharge energy (*with a range of 2 hexagons maximum*). The energy gain is 10 points if

the drone is positioned on the tile, 7 points at a distance of one tile, and 4 energy points at a distance of two tiles (*7 charging station tiles on the terrain*).

▼ Hydrothermal Vent

This tile is blocking and energy-costly : it cannot be crossed in a single move, and one must stop on it. Additionally, it involves an extra energy cost of 3 points when stopping on it.

This type of tile is used for a neutral scientific study mission (*2 hydrothermal vent tiles on the terrain*).

▼ Mined Zone

This tile is used in the game within the context of an allied mine clearance mission (*2 mined zone tiles on the terrain*).

If a drone leaves this tile without it having been cleared, it explodes and loses the game.

▼ Target Zone to Mine

This tile is used for an enemy mining mission (*2 target zone to mine tiles on the terrain*).

If the Reco drone leaves this tile while it has been mined by Suspect, it explodes and loses the game.

▼ Target Zone for Pipeline Destruction

This tile is used for an enemy sabotage mission (*only one tile of this type on the terrain*).

▼ Damaged Pipeline Zone

This tile is used for an allied repair mission (*only one tile of this type on the terrain*).

▼ Target Zone for Fiber Optic Cable Hacking

This tile is used for an enemy hacking mission (*only one tile of this type on the terrain*).

▼ Current Associated with a Scientific Mission

The rules associated with this tile are the same as for a standard current, but it is also associated with a neutral scientific study mission (*4 current tiles are of this type and are divided between two scientific missions*).

The location of the tiles involved in Suspect's missions presented above is explained in detail later (*see section L*).

G. Effects of Currents

Currents can induce a modification in the energy cost of movement and, as detailed below, they are also sometimes blocking or can drift the drone located there.

The change in energy cost associated with movement through a current tile only occurs if the current tile is crossed or stopped upon (*and not if the current tile is the starting point of the movement*).

In cases where the current favors movement, a minimum movement cost of 1 energy point is imposed : regardless of the movement and the direction of the current, the energy cost is necessarily greater than or equal to 1 point.

When passing through a current tile, several cases are possible :

- ⇒ If the movement and the current are aligned and in the same direction, then the movement's energy cost is decreased by 2 points.
- ⇒ If the movement is angled and follows the direction of the current, then the movement's energy cost is decreased by 2 points.

Here, the exit angle between the current and the drone is zero ; which provides an energy bonus of 2 points.

- ⇒ If the movement is in a straight line in the opposite direction of the current, then the movement's energy cost is increased by 3 points and one must stop on the current tile.
- ⇒ If the movement is angled and, upon exit, in the opposite direction to the current, then the movement's energy cost is increased by 3 points and one must stop on the current tile.

Here, the exit angle between the current and the drone is 180° ; which provides an energy penalty of 3 points and a blockage.

- ⇒ If the movement is in a straight line and makes a 60° angle with the current, then the movement's energy cost is decreased by 1 point.
- ⇒ If the movement is angled and makes, upon exit, a 60° angle with the current, then the movement's energy cost is decreased by 1 point.

Here, the exit angle between the current and the drone is 60° , providing an energy bonus of 1 point.

- ⇒ If the movement is in a straight line and makes a 120° angle with the current, then the movement's energy cost is increased by 1 point.

⇒ If the movement is angled and makes, upon exit, a 120° angle with the current, then the movement's energy cost is increased by 1 point.

Here, the exit angle between the current and the drone is 120° , which involves an energy penalty of 1 point.

Also, if a drone is initially on a current tile and the action performed is not a movement, then the drone is drifted by 1 tile in the direction of the current after completing the action.

H. Systematic Passive Sonar

Both Reco and Suspect drones possess a passive sonar which constitutes an energy-free and systematic action at the beginning of each turn.

■ Using Passive Sonar

This action, with zero energy cost, consists of a circular detection within a range of 4 tiles around the drone. If the opposing drone is detected, passive sonar allows for obtaining only its direction, not its precise position or orientation.

In fact, in the event of detection, there is a measurement error regarding the exact direction given by the passive sonar (*uncertainty*). This error results in obtaining not a precise direction but a cone in which the detected object is located. To do this, the gamemaster must show on the map an equilateral triangle with a

side of 4 hexagons (*thus a set of 10 hexagons*) where one vertex is adjacent to the sonar user's tile and which contains the detected object's tile.

In cases where there are two possible choices for this uncertainty triangle (*corresponding to the situation where the detected drone is at a distance greater than or equal to 2 hexagons*), the gamemaster chooses the triangle's position randomly using a 6-sided die : for a result of 1, 2, or 3, they show the triangle with the opening direction most aligned with the orientation of the drone that performed the sonar ping.

The gamemaster always rolls the die so as not to give additional clues to the players and presents the uncertainty triangle on the map using a template.

There are exceptions to the passive sonar rule : if the opposing drone is in a sonar undetectability zone (*see acoustic interference tile presented in section F.*), or if a mountain is present between the two drones, then nothing is detected.

When a mountain is located between the drones, it must be on a tile crossed by the straight line connecting the centers of the hexagons where the two drones are located to prevent detection.

► Furthermore, in the special case where both drones are on the same tile, they detect each other's position regardless of passive sonar (*even in a sonar undetectability zone*). This also applies in a blind zone.

I. Actions Available for Reco

In addition to passive sonar, Reco must perform one and only one action each turn from the list below.

■ Move

There are several types of possible movements : straight movement of 2 tiles and angled moves to the right or left of 2 tiles cost 3 energy points. These movements can be extended by 1 tile, but the energy cost becomes 6. The extended movement costing 6 energy points can also correspond to two tiles in a straight line followed by an angled move of 1 tile.

Finally, two other types of movements consist of a forward or backward step of 1 tile accompanied by a possible change in orientation of 60° or 120° :

- ⇒ A forward step of 1 tile with an orientation change of 0 or 60° costs 3 energy points.
- ⇒ A forward step of 1 tile with an orientation change of 120° costs 4 energy points.
- ⇒ A backward step of 1 tile with an orientation change of 0 or 60° costs 5 energy points.
- ⇒ A backward step of 1 tile with an orientation change of 120° costs 6 energy points.

All possible movements classified by energy cost and type are summarized below.

- Classic movements costing 3 energy points :

- Extended movements costing 6 energy points :

- Forward moves of 1 tile followed by a possible 60° orientation change costing 3 energy points :

- Forward moves of 1 tile followed by a 120° orientation change costing 4 energy points :

- Backward moves of 1 tile followed by a possible 60° orientation change costing 5 energy points :

- Backward moves of 1 tile followed by a 120° orientation change costing 6 energy points :

■ Pass Turn

This action costs no energy.

■ Recharge near a station

When located on the charging station, this action results in an energy gain of 10 points. Recharging can also occur at a distance of 1 or 2 tiles from the station : the drone then gains 7 or 4 energy points respectively.

■ Use Advanced Sonar SAS

This action has an energy cost of 6 points and allows detection within a 60° angle up to a range of 12 tiles. When the opposing drone is detected at a distance less than or equal to 4 tiles, its exact position and orientation are obtained.

Beyond 4 tiles, detection does not give orientation : between 5 and 8 tiles, only the exact position is obtained, and between 9 and 12 tiles, the position is given with a certain measurement error.

In the event of detection at a distance less than or equal to 8 tiles, the gamemaster indicates the exact position of the opposing drone to the sonar user (*as well as its orientation in the closest 4-tile range zone*).

The player who performed the detection can then use a non-oriented token or a drone pawn with orientation to mark this configuration.

If detection occurs between 9 and 12 tiles away, the gamemaster does not indicate the opposing drone's precise position but a circular cluster of 7 tiles, one of which corresponds to the opposing drone's position; this reflects the measurement uncertainty for this long-distance detection.

This circular set of 7 tiles is chosen randomly by the gamemaster by rolling an 8-sided die : for results 7 and 8, they center the uncertainty zone on the detected drone's tile. Conversely, when the die result is between 1 and 6, the center of the uncertainty cluster must be located on one of the detected drone's neighboring hexagons, each neighboring tile being associated with an integer between 1 and 6 (*thus, there is twice as much chance of finding the drone at the center of the uncertainty zone than on the sides*).

This principle regarding the choice of the uncertainty zone with an eight-sided die is summarized below :

Thus, regarding the detection example in the figure at the top of the page, the gamemaster rolled a 4 on the eight-sided die.

The gamemaster can display this uncertainty zone on the map using a template.

Advanced sonar SAS consists of active detection : when the opposing drone is detected, it also receives information about our direction. This information is accompanied, as before, by a measurement error (*but this occurs regardless of the distance between the two drones*) : the gamemaster does not indicate the precise direction of the sonar user to the detected drone but shows an equilateral triangle with a side of 12 tiles where one vertex is adjacent to the detected drone's tile and which contains the location of the drone that used the sonar.

When the detected drone is more than one tile away from the sonar user, there are always two possible choices for such a triangle.

The gamemaster then proceeds in a manner analogous to that explained for passive sonar to determine the uncertainty triangle to show : they roll a six-sided die, where three of the faces are assigned to the triangle with the central opening direction most aligned with the drone's orientation (*faces 1, 2, and 3 will be used for this*).

For this mutual detection due to the active nature of advanced sonar SAS, the gamemaster always rolls the six-sided die so as not to give any additional indication to the players. The uncertainty triangle is shown on the terrain map with a template.

There are also exceptions to these rules : this is the case where the opposing drone is in a sonar undetectability zone (*see acoustic interference tile, section F.*), or when a mountain is present on the straight line connecting the two drones (*specifically, the mountain is intersected by the line connecting the centers of the hexagons associated with the drones' positions*). In these two situations, no detection occurs.

■ Use ML Smart Imagery

The energy cost of this action is 6 points and it allows Reco to obtain, in addition to the position and orientation of the drone, information on Suspect's mission equipment provided that the latter is within a range of 4 tiles around them.

Indeed, if Suspect is in this proximity, one of their mission equipment action cards is randomly revealed to Reco. Note that the gamemaster systematically introduces an additional card representing the failure to obtain information by ML camera among Suspect's cards in the draw. Thus, since the Suspect player initially possesses two action cards associated with mission equip-

ment, ML camera detection fails with a probability of $1/3$.

Regarding Suspect's position and orientation, they are always revealed exactly to Reco when using the ML camera, provided Suspect is at a maximum range of 4 tiles.

■ Use Magnetometer

This detection action is passive (*meaning the detected drone obtains no information about the presence of the user*) and costs 3 energy points. It allows Reco to detect the Suspect drone within a range of 4 tiles around them : if Suspect is detected at a distance between 1 and 3 tiles from Reco, the latter obtains its position and orientation. Beyond that, only the position is revealed.

This detection is precise and involves no measurement error.

■ Use Communication Node

This action is only possible at a distance less than or equal to 1 tile from a communication node. It allows Reco to contact their hierarchy to announce Suspect's mission. Concretely, when this action is performed, the Reco player announces aloud the mission they believe Suspect has; in the case of an allied or neutral mission, and if it is indeed the mission assigned to Suspect, then Reco wins the game. Conversely, if Reco is wrong about the opponent's mission, they lose the game.

This action involves an energy cost of 3 points if Reco is on the communication node and 4 points when they are at a distance of one tile.

■ Deploy Communication Buoy

This action is similar to the previous one, but it can be performed anywhere on the terrain. However, it has the constraint of forcing Reco to pass a turn before announcing Suspect's mission.

It is a low-energy cost action : the cost is 1 point.

■ Fire a Torpedo

Firing a torpedo has an energy cost of 6 points and can be performed only twice.

The torpedo is fired in the direction and sense of Reco's orientation, and its path must measure at most 14 tiles with turns inclined at 60° at most. The Reco player decides the path followed by their torpedo.

If Suspect is at a distance less than or equal to 1 tile from the torpedo's end point, it is destroyed. Furthermore, if Suspect is present on the torpedo's trajectory, it is also neutralized.

Here is an example of a path followed by a torpedo ; it is specifically of length equal to 12 tiles.

J. Default Actions for Suspect

In addition to passive sonar, the Suspect player must perform a single action from those listed in the following sections. Unlike Reco, for whom all actions are default, Suspect has certain default actions and others, called mission equipment actions, which are assigned to them according to their mission.

Suspect's default actions are explained below.

■ Move

Suspect's movement function is the same as for Reco (*see section I.*).

■ Pass Turn

Its operation is the same as for Reco (*see section I.*).

■ Recharge near a station

Suspect's charging function is the same as for Reco (*see section I.*).

K. Equipment Actions

Depending on their mission, Suspect receives two additional action possibilities, one of which is characteristic of the mission to be accomplished (*the equipment given to Suspect for each mission is specified in the next section*).

The actions authorized based on mission equipment are :

■ Use Magnetometer

It works as for Reco (see section I.).

This action is possible for allied or neutral missions (*see mission details below*).

■ Use Water and Sediment Sampler

This action, with an energy cost of 3 points, is necessary to complete the neutral mission in the fiber optic cable zone. It must be performed on each of the two dedicated tiles on the map.

■ Use Physico-chemical Sensors

This action, with an energy cost of 3 points, is necessary to complete the neutral mission in the damaged pipeline zone. It must be performed on each of the two dedicated marine current tiles on the map.

■ Use High-Resolution Camera

This action has a cost of 4 energy points and allows for the neutral mission around the volcanoes as well as the allied mission in the fiber optic cable zone. Suspect's high-resolution camera has a range of 1 tile.

The high-resolution camera is, indeed, usable to observe the hydrothermal vents in the case of the zone 2 neutral mission and to cover the entire fiber optic cable for the zone 1 allied mission.

■ Drop Explosive Charges for Mine Clearance

This action, with an energy cost equal to 3 points, is necessary to complete the allied mission in the partially mined volcano zone. It must be performed on each of the two tiles with mines on the map.

■ Use Articulated Mechanical Arm for Repairs

This action, with an energy cost equal to 4 points, is necessary to complete the allied mission in the damaged pipeline zone. It must be performed on a certain pipeline tile corresponding to the crack.

■ Use Articulated Mechanical Arm for Mine Laying

This action, with an energy cost of 5 points, allows finishing the mining of the volcano zone. It is necessary to complete the enemy mining mission and must be performed on the two dedicated target tiles.

■ Self-Destruct

This action, with an energy cost of 4 points, allows the destruction of the pipeline through a kamikaze operation. It is necessary to complete the enemy sabotage mission on the pipeline and must be performed on the appropriate target tile.

■ Use Opto-electronic Articulated Mechanical Arm

This action has a high energy cost : 7 points. It allows for hacking the fiber optic cable and is necessary to complete the zone 1 enemy espionage mission. It must be performed on the dedicated target tile.

■ Place a Decoy and Move

To perform this action, Suspect must pay 2 energy points in addition to the movement cost. The use of decoys is possible at most three times during the game.

This action allows emitting a means of torpedo avoidance while moving. The decoy is then placed on the initial tile before movement. When a torpedo fired by Reco encounters a decoy on its path, it explodes and destroys the decoy, leaving Suspect unharmed. Similarly, if at the end of its trajectory, the torpedo explodes within a 1-tile distance of the decoy, the decoy is destroyed as a priority and not Suspect (*even if Suspect is also within 1 tile of the explosion*).

Suspect can place up to three decoys, each decoy having a lifespan of 4 turns.

For the execution of this action, the "place a decoy" action card must be shown face up to the gamemaster discreetly while handing them a movement card.

This action is only possible for enemy missions.

L. Possible Missions for Suspect

Suspect wins the game if they successfully carry out their mission before Reco determines their intentions and blocks them or shares them with their hierarchy.

The different missions divided by the three zones are specified here.

★ Zone 1 - Fiber Optic Cable Zone

⊗ **Allied Mission [A1]** : Suspect is an allied maintenance drone and must monitor the fiber optic cable.

⇒ Suspect must use their high-resolution camera along the cable (6 tiles to cover / possible in two moves).

⇒ Their two mission equipments are the high-resolution camera and the magnetometer.

⊗ **Enemy Mission [E1]** : Suspect is an enemy spy drone and must perform a "man-in-the-middle attack" on the fiber optic cable.

⇒ Suspect must activate their articulated mechanical arm equipped with an opto-electronic system on the target tile of the fiber optic cable.

⇒ Their two mission equipments are the opto-electronic articulated mechanical arm and the decoys.

⊗ **Neutral Mission [N1]** : Suspect is a neutral scientific drone and must study flora and pollution near the fiber op-

tic cable.

⇒ Suspect must activate their water and sediment sampler on the two dedicated current tiles near the fiber optic cable.

⇒ Their two mission equipments are the water and sediment sampler and the magnetometer.

★ Zone 2 - Partially Mined Site Near Volcanoes

⊗ **Allied Mission [A2]** : Suspect is an allied mine-clearing drone and must completely clear the area.

⇒ Suspect must use their explosive charge release system for mine clearance on the two mined tiles near the hydrothermal vents.

⇒ Their two mission equipments are the explosive charges for mine clearance and the magnetometer.

⊗ **Enemy Mission [E2]** : Suspect is an enemy mining drone and must finish mining the area.

⇒ Suspect must use their articulated mechanical arm equipped with a mine-laying system on the two target tiles near the volcanoes.

⇒ Their two mission equipments are their mine-release system and the decoys.

⊗ **Neutral Mission [N2]** : Suspect is a neutral scientific drone and must study the two hydrothermal vents.

- ⇒ Suspect must activate their high-resolution camera to cover the two volcano tiles.
- ⇒ Their two mission equipments are their high-resolution camera and the magnetometer.

★ Zone 3 - Damaged Pipeline Zone

⊗ **Allied Mission [A3]** : Suspect is an allied maintenance drone and must repair the pipeline.

- ⇒ Suspect must use their articulated mechanical arm for repair on the tile representing a crack in the pipeline.
- ⇒ Their two mission equipments are their repair mechanical arm and the magnetometer.

⊗ **Enemy Mission [E3]** : Suspect is an enemy destructive drone and must sabotage the pipeline.

- ⇒ Suspect must self-destruct (*kamikaze mission*) on the pipeline target tile.
- ⇒ Their two mission equipments are their self-destruction system and the decoys.

⊗ **Neutral Mission [N3]** : Suspect is a neutral scientific drone and must study marine currents near the pipeline.

- ⇒ Suspect must activate their physico-chemical sensors on the two dedicated current tiles near the pipeline.
- ⇒ Their two mission equipments are their physico-chemical sensors and the magnetometer.

M. Action Priority Rules

To resolve the two actions chosen by the players, the gamemaster must follow the priority rules below. Actions are listed from highest priority down.

1. Passive sonar
2. Placing a decoy
3. Torpedo fire
4. Use of ML camera
5. Movement
6. Advanced sonar SAS and magnetometer
7. Physico-chemical sensors, water and sediment samplers, high-resolution camera, mine clearance, repair, mine laying, self-destruction, and hacking
8. Use of a buoy or communication node
9. Recharging and passing a turn